

The Relationship among Organizational Communication, Knowledge Sharing, and Learning Organizations: A Conceptual Evaluation¹

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Abstract

In recent years, with the technological developments, globalization and the changing structure of organizations, competition has increased and the most important factor in the survival of organizations has become the performance of adaptation to change. Organizations adaptation to global changes, self-renewal and competitiveness are based on knowledge. In today's world where knowledge has become the most important resource, knowledge is of vital importance for organizations to continue their activities and provide increasing and changing respond to increasing and changing market demands. The process of producing, sharing and using knowledge and the management of this process are extremely important for organizations to ensure sustainable competition. Knowledge occurs at the personal level and becomes valuable and available when shared. Communication is required for knowledge to be shared. Communication is the process of conveying feelings, thoughts, ideas, and knowledge to the recipient in any form. Sharing of knowledge is only possible through communication. In this context, the conceptual relationship between organizational communication and knowledge sharing and learning organizations has been put forward in this study to respond to the demands, create innovations and competitive advantage.

Key Words: Organizational Communication, Knowledge Sharing, Learning Organizations

Örgütsel İletişim ve Bilgi Paylaşımının Öğrenen Organizasyonlar ile İlişkisi: Kavramsal Bir Değerlendirme

Öz

Son yıllarda teknolojik gelişmeler, küreselleşme ve örgütlerin değişen yapısı ile birlikte rekabet artmış ve örgütlerin hayatta kalmasında en önemli etken değişime uyum sağlayabilme performansı haline gelmiştir. Örgütlerin küresel değişimlere uyum sağlaması, kendini yenilemesi ve rekabet gücü kazanması ise bilgi temelinde gerçekleşmektedir. Bilginin en önemli kaynak haline geldiği günümüzde örgütlerin faaliyetlerini sürdürebilmesi, artan ve değişen taleplere cevap verebilmesi, yenilikler yaratabilmesi ve rekabet avantajı sağlayabilmesi için bilgi hayati önem taşımaktadır. Bilginin üretilmesi, paylaşılması ve kullanılması süreci ve bu sürecin yönetimi örgütlerin sürdürülebilir rekabeti sağlayabilmeleri için son derece önemlidir. Bilgi kişisel düzeyde oluşur ve paylaşıldığı zaman değerli ve kullanılabilir hale gelir. Bilginin paylaşılabilmesi için iletişim gereklidir. İletişim kaynağın duygu, düşünce, fikir ve bilgilerini herhangi bir yolla alıcıya göndermesi sürecidir. Bilginin paylaşılması ise ancak iletişim ile gerçekleşmektedir. Bu bağlamda çalışmada, örgütsel iletişim ve bilgi paylaşımının öğrenen organizasyonlar ile arasındaki kavramsal ilişki ortaya konulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Örgütsel İletişim, Bilgi Paylaşımı, Öğrenen Organizasyonlar

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Introduction

Today, technological advances and globalisation have created a profound transformation process that deeply affects organisations. Changing customer expectations, intense competition and the constant need for innovation have led organisations to become agile, learning and knowledge-based structures. To maintain a competitive advantage and achieve sustainable success, organisations must not only utilise existing knowledge but also have the capacity to generate, share, and apply new knowledge. At this point, knowledge has become a strategic and irreplaceable asset for organisations. An organization's capacity for innovation and adaptation is based on its capacity to access, process, and replicate knowledge. Senge's (1990) learning organization approach highlights how important knowledge sharing, effective communication, a common vision, and ongoing learning are to the growth of an organization. Only through efficient communication and knowledge-sharing procedures can learning occur at the organizational level. Employee knowledge transfer, experience sharing, and organizational memory development are all facilitated by open, two-way, trust-based communication structures. Consequently, one of the most important factors influencing knowledge sharing and organizational learning is communication within the organization. In order to provide a comprehensive viewpoint in the literature, this study aims to investigate the connections among organizational communication, organizational learning, and knowledge sharing within a theoretical framework. Organizations' ability to learn, communicate effectively, and foster a culture of knowledge sharing are critical in today's business environment, where knowledge has emerged as a key differentiator. By examining the relationships between these three ideas from a comprehensive standpoint, this study seeks to advance the theory and application of organizational transformation, innovation, and sustainable success processes. Furthermore, it is expected to contribute to the field by presenting a comprehensive analysis of these three ideas, which are under discussion due to the lack of any examination in the literature in this context.

In this regard, the study seeks to clarify the conceptual connection among learning organizations, knowledge sharing, and organizational communication. The following are the study's primary research questions:

RQ1. What is the conceptual relationship between organisational communication, knowledge sharing and learning organisations?

RQ2. How does effective organisational communication support knowledge sharing processes and the capacity to become a learning organisation?

The study examines the concepts of organisational communication, knowledge sharing and learning organisations within a theoretical framework. In line with the study's objective, these concepts are defined in detail, and their possible relationships are discussed based on the literature. The research only conducts a conceptual analysis, which constitutes the main limitation of the study. It is recommended that future research transform these relationships into applied studies by testing them with empirical data.

The first section of the study explains organisational communication, the second section explains knowledge sharing, and the third section explains the concept of the learning organisation. The relationship between the concepts is discussed in the fourth section, and the conclusions are presented in the results and evaluation section.

1. The Concept of Organisational Communication

Communication is of vital importance in human relations and in every area where humans are involved. The interaction, existence, and sustainability of individuals and organisations are based on communication. The dictionary definition of the word communication is "the transfer of feelings, thoughts, or information to others by any means imaginable..." (Turkish Language Association). Communication is the process of transferring information and meaning between a source and a receiver using one or more communication channels (Bovee and Thill, 2018: 4). Robbins and Judge (2019: 342) define communication as a process that includes not only the transfer of information or interpretations between a source and a receiver, but also the understanding of this information and these interpretations by the receiver. Timuroğlu and Balkaya (2016:92)

define communication as "the process of conveying and understanding meaning." Miller (2011), however, argues that communication involves more than just the process of transmitting a message from the source to the receiver by any means and that it has a more complex structure. He states that today's world, which has become a network of complex systems, has created an even more complex communication process. Miller suggests that communication is related to computers connecting people through complex networks, the formation of meaning systems in families and cultures, understanding the market to increase sales in an organisation, and understanding the issues that unite and divide societies (Miller, 2011: 12-13). The communication process diagram is shown in Table 1

Figure 1. Communication Process

The communication process diagram, adapted from Baykal's (1981) work, is presented in Figure 1.

In an effective communication process, the source encodes the message they wish to send—that is, their ideas, information, attitudes, thoughts, or feelings—and transmits it to the receiver via an appropriate channel (such as telephone, courier, email, social media, internet, or verbal communication) according to their own values and objectives. The process continues with the decoding stage, where the receiver perceives and interprets the message, and is completed with the receiver's feedback (response). In this context, the elements of source, encoding, message, channel, receiver, decoding, and feedback are necessary for an effective communication process (Koçel, 2020: 542-549; Gül, 2018: 201-202; Griffin and Moorhead, 2013: 300-302).

Maintaining effective communication is crucial in preventing misunderstandings between the sender and the recipient, and in ensuring that the intended message is conveyed accurately. There are certain factors that prevent communication from functioning fully and effectively through the aforementioned elements. These factors can be listed as follows (Lunenburg, 2010: 3-6).

Barriers to the process: Every element involved in the communication process is important. Therefore, each element must be fully and clearly realised for effective communication. Barriers to the process include the source being unable to express themselves clearly, incorrect encoding, initiating the communication process when emotions are running high, the communication channel not being appropriately selected for the message, the receiver being unable to decode the message as intended due to interpersonal differences, the message being incompletely conveyed because the source is not fully focused on the message, and the source thinking that the message has not been conveyed or understood due to a lack of feedback.

Physical barriers: Physical barriers arise from environmental conditions outside the communication process (Rani, 206: 76). Examples of physical barriers include noise, disruptions in the chosen communication channel, and distracting environmental conditions.

Semantic barriers: Semantic barriers arise when the receiver fails to perceive the message sent by the source as intended. Words may not convey the same meaning to everyone. Several variables, including a person's

culture, upbringing, gender, and age, can contribute to this situation. When the meaning the source assigns to the words they choose does not match the recipient's interpretation of the message, the communication process is negatively affected. Therefore, it is important for both the source and the recipient to consider the characteristics of the other party when encoding or decoding the message.

Psychosocial barriers: Psychosocial barriers encompass the experiential domain, filtering, and psychological distance. The experiential domain consists of a person's past, needs, prejudices, values, and expectations. The source creates and encodes the message within its own experiential domain. Effective communication can occur to the extent that the experiential domains of the source and the receiver overlap. Filtering causes us to perceive the message in a way that aligns with our own perceptions. It enables the person to perceive the message in light of their needs and expectations. Robbins and Judge (2019: 359) define filtering as the source shaping the message according to the receiver's desires and expectations. In other words, filtering is performed by both the source and the receiver. While the source can encode the message according to the receiver, the receiver can also decode the message according to their own desires and expectations. Interpersonal psychological distance, on the other hand, relates to individuals' perceptions of communication processes. Psychological distance can be defined as the degree of positivity perceived in communication based on the mental evaluations of individuals with different cultural backgrounds, statuses, and values (Chen and Li, 2017: 3).

The obstacles encountered prevent the communication process from continuing as desired, leading to misunderstandings and problems. Obstacles to communication should be minimised as much as possible, and an effective communication process should be ensured. Communication is of vital importance at both the individual and organisational levels. The fundamental phenomenon in the formation of organisations (Koçel, 2020: 102), which are established by two or more people for a specific purpose and are part of the social structure, is a "common purpose". Communication is at the core of organisations that continue as a system of activities and relationships centred around a common purpose. Communication plays the most important role in the formation of organisations and serves as the fundamental element that enables individuals to unite around a common purpose. An organisation consists of the mutual behaviours and relationships of the individuals who form it towards a common purpose. Organisations, which can also be seen as small societies within themselves, have their own structures and characteristics (Karcıoğlu, Timuroğlu and Çınar, 2009: 63-64). The structure and characteristics of the organisation are shaped by communication. It is almost impossible for people to shape their daily lives without communicating. Similarly, communication forms the fundamental condition for sustainable activity and structure within organisations. Harmony, knowledge sharing, coordination, the development of the organisation's environmental relations and adaptation to conditions within the organisation are all based on effective communication. The growth of organisations, along with factors such as technology and globalisation, has made organisational structures more complex, and the importance of knowledge sharing and effective communication for the organisation to continue its activities has increased day by day (Karaçor and Şahin, 2004: 100). Previously, manager-employee communication in organisations was based on orders necessary to achieve organisational goals. Today, however, due to the impact of global changes, a more complex communication network is required. The increasing number of levels and units within organisations necessitates the formation of a more complex and effective communication network (Can, 1992: 247). The measure of effective communication in organisations is the recipient's demonstration of the expected behaviours in response to the message's content, the desired development of the employee's functions (Halis, 2000: 222), and the provision of the necessary information flow. Organisational communication occurs in two distinct ways: formal and informal communication. Every organisation possesses both formal and informal communication networks (Bovee and Thill, 2018: 8).

1.1. Formal Communication

Formal communication is a form of communication that occurs through the flow of messages determined by hierarchy or job function (Goldhaber, 1986: 165). Generally following the hierarchical structure of the organisation, formal communication is defined as the transmission of work-related information by the organisation to its members and the degree of transmission between members (Kandlousi, Ali and Abdollahi,

2010: 52). Formal communication occurs through vertical, horizontal, and cross-channel means within the organisation (Gül, 2018: 203).

Vertical communication channels: Vertical communication occurs in two ways: top-down and bottom-up. Shaped by the hierarchical structure within the organisation, vertical communication facilitates the flow of information from manager to employee and from employee to manager. In top-down communication, messages such as rules, procedures, information requests, objectives, discipline, policies, and information aimed at ensuring group unity are conveyed from the manager to the employee (Goldhaber, 1986: 166). Bottom-up communication, on the other hand, refers to the ability of employees to convey information about their work and their thoughts about management to higher-level management. Both types of vertical communication are important for improving the employees' attitude and thoughts towards the organisation and increasing their motivation. It is also important for the organisation to achieve its goals that employees can convey their thoughts to managers and that managers provide the necessary information to employees. However, there are some obstacles to bottom-up communication (Can, 1992: 249-250):

- Due to the existence of many levels within organisations, employees may experience difficulties in reaching senior management, and due to the increasing number of levels, it is necessary for the communication process to take place without skipping any level of the hierarchical structure.
- In the communication process that takes place according to the hierarchical order, the message that the employee wants to convey may undergo changes depending on how it is interpreted at each level.
- The employee is unable to convey their thoughts to the manager as they wish due to the manager's attitude and behaviour.
- The employee is unable to meet with the manager when they wish and is forced to convey their views through an intermediary.
- Upward communication is not as widespread as downward communication, and the organisation's perspective on upward communication.

Managers play a crucial role in ensuring that bottom-up communication occurs effectively. The manager's attitude and behaviour towards employees create barriers to bottom-up communication. Therefore, changing the manager's attitude and behaviour will positively influence employee-manager interaction and ensure effective communication. In his study involving 16 organisations, Goldhaber identified deficiencies in knowledge sharing in the top-down communication process and listed these deficiencies as follows (Goldhaber, 1986: 168):

- Employees are unable to obtain sufficient information from the organisation.
- Employees' primary information needs are personal information related to their work (salary, how the work is done, social benefits, etc.) and information about the organisational decision-making process (plans, failures, decisions, etc.).
- Employees' difficulties in obtaining information about the organisation from senior management and information about their work from managers.
- Information from senior management is of lower quality than information from key sources, and untimely information negatively affects the quality of information at the organisational level

Horizontal communication channels: Horizontal communication is communication that occurs between units and members of equal status within the hierarchical structure of an organisation (Gül, 2018: 204). Horizontal communication facilitates coordination and saves time (Robbins and Judge, 2018, p. 346).

Cross-communication channels: Cross-communication occurs between individuals who are not at the same level in the organisational hierarchy but work in different units (Can, 1992, p. 252).

1.2. Informal Communication

Most of the work that employees do in organisations requires cooperation and collaboration. Group members need to communicate in order to perform their jobs and social functions. Groups within organisations are also involved in communication, just like group members (Kraut et al. 1990: 148). Individuals who come

together for cooperation within an organisation develop relationships by discovering commonalities, and the informal communication process begins.

Informal communication occurs through social interaction between individuals (Kandlousi, Ali, and Abdollahi, 2010: 52). In addition to formal communication networks, every organisation generally has informal communication networks, often referred to as gossip, rumour mills, or whispering networks. Informal networks emerge spontaneously when employees come together because formal networks often fail to provide the desired information. The limitations of formal communication networks have led to the development of social networks within organisations and the proliferation of social media within organisations, enabling the sharing of information that formal networks cannot capture in relation to work. However, the effective use of informal communication networks is crucial (Bovee and Thill, 2018: 8). These untraceable communication networks may provide inaccurate information and cause confusion within the organisation.

Informal communication networks tend to develop reactively during times of greater uncertainty and anxiety (Robbins and Judge, 2018: 350). The failure to effectively establish bottom-up communication, coupled with the aforementioned lack of knowledge sharing in this communication style, can be said to contribute to the creation of an environment of anxiety and uncertainty, thereby leading to the emergence of rumours. Informal communication tends to progress more rapidly than formal communication. Research indicates that trust in information obtained from informal networks is high among employees, but managers view this information with scepticism (Goldhaber, 1986: 176).

2. The Concept of Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge is a flow of meaning that can increase, restructure, and change information (Nonaka, 1994: 15). In other words, knowledge is the process of organising data (Avcı and Avcı, 2004) to increase information and make it meaningful and useful. In addition to information always having an important place in organisations, information has been recognised as the most important resource for organisations in recent years. Information constitutes the most important source of an organisation's competitive strength and sustainability (Ipe, 2003: 337). The common view of organisational managers, consultants and academics is that organisational knowledge constitutes a key strategic resource for the organisation. Knowledge, an irreplaceable and unique abstract concept, has become the primary focus of managerial interest (Cabrera and Cabrera, 2002: 688).

Today, technology, world affairs, fashion, interests and trends are changing rapidly. Organisations have become the closest followers of change in order to respond to the changing world and its evolving expectations. Therefore, the acquisition, sharing and effective use of information within organisations is extremely important. The pace of change has also impacted societies, leading to the emergence of a global consumer culture. The development and growth of organisations, which have broken away from national borders to become transnational corporations, has increased global competition. As a result, the continuous renewal of products and services has also gained importance. Diversity and innovation have become crucial concepts for driving competition, and meeting consumer demands has become increasingly challenging due to the competitive environment. New products are constantly being launched, and consumers are offered a wide variety of services. In a world where innovation and change are crucial, "information" is a basic requirement for businesses to stay in business and become more competitive. The quick adoption of new products and services by consumers has forced businesses to grow, diversify, and update their offerings. Organizations' intangible assets have grown in importance as a differentiating competitive factor in today's knowledge-based economy, with employee knowledge and organizational reputation serving as the key components of competitive advantage. In a world that is changing quickly, businesses must constantly update their understanding of the laws, suppliers, competitors, and customer expectations. Even though the value of knowledge sharing for organizations is becoming more widely recognized, information accessibility is still restricted. Information that is kept in secret or difficult-to-access documents is a barrier to Access (Riege, 2005: 18).

Information exists in organisations in two ways. It manifests itself as tacit (person-dependent/implicit) and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge refers to information stored in people's minds, encompassing both cognitive and technical elements. Tacit knowledge encompasses both the perspective formed by a person's

beliefs and perceptions, as well as the concrete technical knowledge comprising craftsmanship and skills. Tacit knowledge is person-dependent. Therefore, it cannot be easily coded and cannot be used without the person who owns the knowledge. Explicit knowledge, on the other hand, is independent of the individual or digital, can be easily stored, and can be used independently of the individual at any desired place and time. Explicit knowledge is recorded information stored in places such as libraries, archives, and databases (Nonaka, 1994: 16-17; Ipe, 2003: 344). The sharing and effective use of information within an organisation are crucial in providing a competitive advantage. Utilising information is only possible when knowledge sharing occurs and new information is created by building upon the knowledge of others. Knowledge sharing between individuals is the process of transforming information into a form that is understandable, assimilable, and usable (Ipe, 2003: 341). Knowledge sharing is the provision and acceptance of information on a specific subject between individuals, groups or units, based on the principle of voluntariness, in accordance with laws and norms, through communication and interaction. Knowledge sharing can take place through formal or informal means (Demirel, 2007: 101). Informal knowledge sharing refers to knowledge sharing that occurs spontaneously, outside of any formal plan. In informal knowledge sharing, individuals share knowledge through face-to-face interactions or via various communication channels, such as telephone or email. Formal knowledge sharing, on the other hand, is a controlled form of knowledge sharing that is carried out under specific conditions, particularly through the use of technology (Yeniçeri and Demirel, 2007: 223).

Haas and Hansen state that knowledge sharing in organisations occurs in two ways. The first form of knowledge sharing is through interpersonal interaction and communication, such as advice. This occurs when members of the organisation give each other advice on how the work is done and how it operates. The distinguishing feature of advice is that it requires direct contact between the source and the recipient of the information. The second way of sharing information, through documents, is done by means of written sources that organisational members share, making their information available to other organisational members. The distinguishing feature of sharing information through documents is the separation between the source and the recipient. The recipient does not need to communicate directly with the source, as the document can be used as an independent source (Haas and Hansen, 2007: 1134-1136).

Curado and Vieira emphasise the importance of trust in knowledge sharing. Members of the organization may be reluctant to share their knowledge because they feel that doing so gives them power (Işık, 2018: 644). This way of thinking stems from a lack of interpersonal trust. This is due to the fact that trust improves interpersonal communication and lowers the perception of risk, which promotes involvement in the information-sharing process. Knowledge sharing between people and between people and the organization is increased when there is a high degree of trust. For knowledge sharing to be more efficient, mutual trust must be evident, and employees' efforts to share information should be recognised and rewarded. A mutual trust environment increases not only knowledge sharing but also employee performance, productivity, and organisational commitment (Curado and Vieira, 2019: 1452).

The knowledge-sharing process, like the communication process, occurs between the source and recipient of information. Therefore, the coding and perception of both the recipient and the source are important. The use of a common language is important for effective knowledge sharing within organisations. Both the source providing the information and the recipient obtaining it must convey and perceive the message correctly. Since information that is not communicated correctly will not be usable at the personal and organisational levels, it is important to implement an effective information-sharing process in order to gain an advantage in a competitive environment and achieve organisational goals.

3. Learning Organisations

Organisations must be able to continuously learn, utilise the knowledge they acquire, apply it, and increase their knowledge for long-term success. The effective organisational learning process, which occurs through knowledge creation and sharing within the organisation, provides foresight into the outcomes of decisions and activities, understanding of environmental conditions, and easy adaptation (Yang, 2007: 85). A learning organisation can be defined as an organisation that evaluates every experience it has as a source of knowledge, produces and shares knowledge, and uses knowledge in all its processes (Koçel, 2020: 435). Learning

organisations are those that do not shy away from making mistakes, evaluating differences of opinion, encouraging learning, change and innovation, and turning every experience, good or bad, into an opportunity for self-improvement (Robbins and Judge, 2019: 605-606).

Senge defines learning organisations as those in which individuals develop their capacity to achieve their goals, new and comprehensive thinking models are created, and shared aspirations are at the forefront. Organisational learning develops only in accordance with individuals' learning tendencies and abilities. An organisation's learning capacity depends on the learning capacity of its members. Senge lists the five fundamental characteristics of learning organisations as follows (Senge, 1994: 8-13; Çakır and Yükseltürk, 2010: 503):

- System-focused thinking: System-focused thinking involves evaluating events and situations as a whole rather than in parts. When events are considered in parts, they do not make complete sense to individuals, but everything that happens is invisibly connected through cause-and-effect relationships.

- Personal expertise: Personal expertise is the continuous development and learning of the individual. Organisational learning occurs through the learning of individuals.

- Mental models: Mental models define individuals' perceptions and thought systems. Mental models are the ways in which individuals interpret the data they obtain through their senses.

- Building a shared vision: Building a shared vision emphasises the importance of all units and individuals within the organisation having common values, goals and a mission. It is essential for the organisation's continuity that people come together around shared values and goals and have a shared vision. A shared vision increases people's motivation to learn.

- Team learning: Team learning occurs when the team acts as a single entity, transcending the differences between its members, and is dependent on communication between team members. Only when teams act as a whole and in a coordinated manner can the team's learning potential exceed the sum of its individual members' potential. Team learning is vital for learning organisations because teams are the fundamental learning units of modern organisations.

Every organisation learns, but to gain strength and survive in a competitive environment, learning must be fast, effective, and continuous. In today's information age, where knowledge is of vital importance to organisations, those that do not engage in an effective learning process and do not build their structure on a foundation of learning face the risk of failure. The learning speed of individuals, units and organisations is seen as the only sustainable competitive advantage, particularly in knowledge-intensive industries. Producing, sharing, using, and ensuring the continuity of new knowledge are fundamental for learning organisations. Learning organisations should be committed to knowledge, value the ideas of their members, encourage learning, constantly renew themselves, and have a structure that is integrated with the outside world (Mills and Friezen, 1992: 146-148). Jo and Joo (2011: 253) discuss seven cultural characteristics of learning organisations: continuous learning, questioning and dialogue, team learning, embedded systems, empowerment, connection with the environment, and strategic leadership.

Learning organisations must be open to ideas from both the external environment and within the organisation. For change to occur, it is necessary to be open to sources of information and to evaluate and analyse all incoming information. Integration with the external environment, effective two-way communication with organisational members, and the attitudes held by the organisation are important for ensuring continuous learning. In learning organisations, the organisational climate must encourage individuals and groups to learn and share knowledge. It is essential for a learning organisation to continually learn, renew itself, foster formal and informal knowledge sharing, adapt its organisational structure to change, value diverse ideas, and provide opportunities for open discussion.

4. Organisational Communication, Knowledge Sharing and the Relationship with Learning Organisations

In today's knowledge-based economy, the most important resource that organizations possess is considered to be knowledge. In this context, knowledge, which is an important competitive tool, appears in two different types in organizational processes: explicit and tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge is easy to communicate,

can be concretized, stored, and transferred. Tacit knowledge, on the other hand, is difficult to transfer; however, it has a higher potential to increase competitive strength because it is difficult for competitors to obtain (Pascoe and More, 2005: 247, 248). Tacit knowledge is usually based on experience and observation and is person-dependent. Increasing interaction among organizational members facilitates the sharing of tacit knowledge. As the level of joint work, observation, and experience gained increases, the production and transfer of tacit knowledge also strengthens (Nonaka, 1994: 19). However, the sustainability of the knowledge produced is also very important. Changing production processes with advancing technology and the increasing diversity of product and service needs affect the sustainability of competition. Organizations must increase their ability to integrate this into organizational processes while ensuring the continuity of the knowledge produced in order to maintain and continue the advantages they have gained over their competitors. In this context, the competitive power of organizations depends not only on knowledge production but also on the correct use of knowledge and its transfer to the organizational level. The important thing here is for the organization to increase its ability to be a learning organization. Learning organizations are organizations where knowledge is continuously produced, evaluated, shared, and used. At the core of a learning organization is the transformation of all positive and negative experiences into knowledge and, at the same time, the creation of an open system that is compatible with the environment. The creation of knowledge takes place on an individual basis. Knowledge is produced by individuals and gains meaning and value in the mental process of the person to whom it belongs. Therefore, the most important steps in creating learning organizations are encouraging individuals to learn, increasing their learning potential, developing their organizational attitudes, supporting knowledge sharing, and improving their ideas about the organization (Garvin, Edmondson and Gino, 2008: 1-3). An individual's motivation to learn depends on the interaction between the organization and the individual. Ensuring effective organizational communication is important for strengthening and maintaining the relationship between the individual and the organization (Kılıç and Saygılı, 2019: 113). Effective organizational communication also encourages individuals' knowledge sharing behavior (Van den Hooff and De Ridder, 2004).

Figure 2. Research model

In other words, it is evident that being a learning organization is not independent of an effective communication process. At this point, both formal and informal communication are quite important for organizations. However, in addition to formal communication that progresses within a defined framework, informal communication is a form of communication that arises spontaneously and responds to social needs. It improves decision-making processes by complementing the weaknesses of formal communication. Furthermore, organizational members gaining knowledge about each other, socializing, and sharing contributes to an increase in the level of trust (Fay, 2011: 214,221). Trust is seen as one of the factors affecting knowledge sharing (Razmerita, Kirchner and Nielsen, 2016: 1229). In this context, ensuring effective organizational communication processes will support knowledge sharing by increasing the level of trust. Ultimately, the model created by the author as a result of the literature review is as Figure 2

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Examining the critical and comprehensive relationship between learning organizations, knowledge sharing, and organizational communication is the goal of this conceptual study. Organizations' ability to adapt to change and engage in knowledge-based renewal is essential to their survival and long-term success in the face of global shifts and a more competitive environment (Robbins and Judge, 2019). Learning organizations, the cornerstone of continuous learning, are strategically significant in this regard (Senge, 1994).

The study's main finding is that knowledge sharing, organizational learning, and the design of a learning organization all depend on efficient organizational communication. According to Nonaka (1994), knowledge is created on an individual basis and only becomes useful and valuable when it is shared. Sharing knowledge requires communication. Both official and informal communication channels are used in organizations to share information. In particular, open, two-way, trust-based communication structures make employees more willing to share information (Van Den Hooff and De Ridder, 2004). It has been noted that employees find it difficult to express themselves due to hierarchical barriers in vertical communication (Rani, 2016) and a lack of feedback, which leads them to withhold information that could be beneficial to the organization (Riege, 2005). Learning organizations are organizations that turn experience into knowledge by embracing the principles of effective knowledge sharing, a shared vision, and ongoing learning (Senge, 1994). The motivational power of organizational communication makes it possible to develop the learning capacity of its members, which is a prerequisite for organizational learning. Only through knowledge sharing made possible by efficient communication can a learning organization achieve the ongoing learning and innovation it demands. Positive attitudes toward the organization and a sense of worth are fostered by effective communication within the organization (Timuroğlu and Balkaya, 2016). This encourages employees to support the desire to share information by increasing their propensity to embrace organizational goals (organizational commitment). Therefore, building trust-based, efficient organizational communication is the top priority in moving toward becoming a learning organization.

Effective communication and knowledge sharing are two fundamental components of Senge's (1994) learning organization approach, and the study theoretically validates their critical importance for organizational learning. The discussion is predicated on the idea that management's attitude, rather than coercion, will shape the learning process, which will take place in a setting of trust and encouragement. Building a learning organization is largely dependent on managers' encouragement of knowledge sharing, receptivity to new ideas, and constructive handling of errors. It has been noted that knowledge sharing and employee dedication to organizational goals are severely harmed by hierarchical barriers that arise in bottom-up communication (many levels, managers' closed attitude to criticism) (Rani, 2016; Robbins and Judge, 2019). This circumstance emphasizes how important it is for businesses to switch from vertical channels of communication to two-way, trust-based systems. According to Van Den Hooff and De Ridder (2004), the idea that informal communication networks enhance the limitations of formal communication by boosting trust and facilitating the quick spread of information highlights the cultural environment that educational organizations ought to promote.

In today's knowledge economy, learning organisations have become increasingly important. For learning organisations to be successfully established, the level of knowledge sharing must be increased. Therefore, it is necessary to first improve organisational communication and strengthen individuals' relationships with other members of the organisation and with the organisation itself. Improving individuals' attitudes towards the organisation and other members will support the formation of a learning organisation by increasing knowledge sharing.

Learning, communication, and knowledge sharing within organisations, which occur at the individual level, are shaped by management's attitude. Learning is not a process that can be forced; individuals' desire to learn must be encouraged. Individuals who have a positive attitude towards the organisation and a sense of organisational commitment will pursue continuous learning on their own accord, and their learning levels and knowledge base will develop. The organisation's attitude of encouraging and supporting learning will also foster a sense of trust in the individual and increase their willingness to share knowledge. Rewarding knowledge sharing is important.

Ultimately, effective organisational communication is a priority for creating learning organisations. Effective organisational communication enhances employee harmony within the organisation and fosters positive feelings towards the organisation. Increasing organisational employee harmony enables progress towards becoming a learning organisation by increasing employees' tendency to embrace organisational goals. Continuous learning, continuous knowledge production, change, adaptation to the environment, effective knowledge sharing and utilisation, which are required for becoming a learning organisation, can be achieved through effective communication. At this point, the most important task falls to managers. An atmosphere that will increase knowledge production and sharing must be created by establishing an effective communication culture within the organization.

The following recommendations are made for researchers: The effectiveness of organisational communication should be measured, particularly in terms of its sub-dimensions such as two-way communication, feedback quality, and open-door policy. A model in which trust and commitment are mediating variables should test the assumption that effective communication increases knowledge sharing not directly, but through the high sense of trust it creates among employees (especially trust in managers) and increased organisational commitment. Organisational commitment is an important motivator for willingness to share information (Timuroğlu and Balkaya, 2016). By considering Organisational Learning and Learning Organisation Capacity as dependent variables, the extent to which knowledge sharing behaviour affects the level of Organisational Learning, which is vital for the organisation's competitive advantage and organisational effectiveness, should be examined. Testing this empirical model will strengthen the theoretical foundation of the conceptual relationship and provide concrete, practical guidance to managers on which communication processes they need to improve in order to create a learning organisation culture.

Ethical Considerations of the Study

It is declared that the study was designed to realistically and ethically meet the needs, and that integrity was maintained in obtaining data, concluding the study, and publishing the results. Ethical committee approval was not required for this research. No research requiring ethics committee approval was conducted in this study.

Informed Consent

There was no need to obtain informed consent from individuals, as the study did not involve any procedures or interventions on human participants.

Author Contributions

Idea/Concept: Z.N.Ç.; Design: Z.N.Ç.; Supervision/Consultancy: Z.N.Ç.; Resources: Z.N.Ç.; Data Collection and/or Processing: Z.N.Ç.; Analysis and/or Interpretation: Z.N.Ç.; Literature Review: Z.N.Ç.; Writing: Z.N.Ç.; Critical Review: Z.N.Ç.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest

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Declarations

This study has not been presented at any congress.

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